

2024
Hackathon
Proceedings

Africa, Law & Emerging Technologies
POLICY HACKATHON

Organised by:

DATA SCIENCE LAW LAB

With support from:

UNIVERSITEIT VAN PRETORIA
UNIVERSITY OF PRETORIA
YUNIBESITHI YA PRETORIA

 Meta

Credits

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Africa, Law & [Emerging] Technologies Policy Hackathon 2024 proceedings report:* Chijioke Okorie (Editor).

**Apart from formatting changes, students' hackathon solutions and expert discourse presentations have been reproduced as is.*

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Note from the Principal Investigator, Data Science Law Lab

Hackathons are events that bring together people with diverse backgrounds to collaborate and create innovative solutions to real-world problems. Our brand of hackathon is a policy hackathon which involves brainstorming and co-creating solutions that address identified policy challenges. Further, this hackathon is called the Africa, Law & [Emerging] Technologies Policy Hackathon! With this brand of policy hackathon, we are acknowledging the increased efforts in recent times, to amplify the voices and representation of Africans and African contexts in shaping the development, governance and use of technologies especially AI systems.

The key aspect in this regard for us this year relates to data in terms of mediating the tension between data privacy and data access, use, reuse and management focusing on vulnerable persons and vulnerable contexts.

[Data Science Law Lab](#) set out two challenge statements working with two challenge partners – the [Centre for Child Law](#), in the Department of Private Law at the University of Pretoria and the [South African National Bioinformatics Institute](#) at the University of the Western Cape, South Africa. The challenge statements are focused on child privacy online and data privacy in the public health contexts.

As we have continued to reiterate at the Data Science Law Lab, the national context and priorities of African countries require a nuanced and sometimes bespoke application of the law and formulation of policy to support and promote AI research, development and application. And the challenges around implementing such nuanced and contextual approach cannot be addressed by one discipline alone. In that light, we are excited that on the platform of the Africa, Law & [Emerging] Technology Policy Hackathon, we can present some of the postgraduate students who submitted solutions and thoughts as to how the challenge presented in child privacy and in public health contexts may or could be addressed. We also have emerging and established experts weighing in with thoughts on those challenges.

One of the most crucial aspects of a successful hackathon is choosing expert judges from diverse contexts and fields and empowering them further with effective judging criteria. Given that the goals of the Africa, Law and emerging technologies policy hackathon include to:

- Encourage innovation and creativity in the development of new ideas and products
- Foster collaboration among participants and stakeholders
- Promote education and learning within our student body
- Address social challenges,

Our judging criteria focused on:

- The originality and creativity of the solution
- The solution's potential for impact
- Scalability, amongst others.

Beyond announcing winners and prizes, the plan is to take winning solutions forward – students working with the experts and our challenge partners to finetune and further develop the winning solutions and hopefully, launch/implement them in the society. All these have been made possible with financial and technical support from **Meta** and the **University of Pretoria, Research Development Grant** and at Data Science Law Lab, we are truly grateful for that support and partnership in moving the research enterprise forward.

Everyone at Data Science Law Lab pitched in to make the Demo Day a success and I thank them immensely.

Dr Chijioke Okorie
University of Pretoria, South Africa
August 2024

Acknowledgements

Africa, Law & Emerging Technologies

POLICY HACKATHON

Thank You...

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About the hackathon

Overview

Africa, Law & [Emerging] Technology Policy Hackathon is a new hackathon convened by [Data Science Law Lab](#) (a research group at the University of Pretoria). The hackathon allows participants to work in teams to develop creative policy solutions to problems posed by diverse partners from academia, government and industry. Participants, who are African postgraduate students presented hacks solo and in teams to the hackathon challenges.

Judging

Judging of the hacks (i.e., the solutions) submitted by hackathon participants was undertaken by a panel of experts drawn from industry, academia, and government, each bringing their unique perspectives to the evaluation process.

Participants submitted a policy memo that outlined their solutions. These submissions were evaluated by the judges in an initial round where they provided feedback and comments to the participants. Following this, the judges shortlisted finalists who presented their solutions on Demo Day – 31 July 2024.

On Demo Day, finalists were invited to present their solutions and engage in a Question-and-Answer session with the judges. Following this session, the judges conducted a second round of deliberations to determine the overall winners, who were recognized with cash prizes.

Challenges presented for hacking

The challenges presented were in two categories: Child privacy on digital platforms and data privacy in public health context. The full challenge statements are available below.

Experts' Discourse

As part of the programme on Demo Day, we invited and received presentations from both emerging and established experts in the fields of data protection and privacy in a segment tagged the '**Experts' Discourse**'.

The goal of the Experts' Discourse was to have data protection and privacy experts from across Africa weigh in with solutions to the challenges posed in our policy hackathon.

Challenge: Child privacy on digital platforms

In collaboration with Centre for Child Law, University of Pretoria

Participants *(in alphabetical order)*

- Paul Apeh, University of Bradford
- Daniel Katongo Chola, University of Pretoria
- Obakeng Ncube, University of Pretoria
- Sibabalwe Nongwana, University of Pretoria
- Mankaleme Ramokgola, University of Pretoria
- Nocebo Sibanda, University of Pretoria
- Qudisiyah Vahed, University of Pretoria

Finalists

- Paul Apeh
- Daniel Katongo Chola
- Sibabalwe Nongwana (Winner)

Challenge Statement

Child privacy on digital platforms

Background

In many jurisdictions including in South Africa, laws, policies and programmes have been enacted and created to protect and secure the privacy of citizens. These efforts, which manifest as a country's privacy protection framework/system, applies to children as well. At the same time, there are significant contextual concerns when it comes to protecting and ensuring the privacy of children in the online/digital environment particularly on digital platforms where exchange happens between the producers of products, services and information, their customers and the general public. There is a wide range of child privacy protection efforts across governments, owners of digital platforms and families.

On one hand, the protection of the privacy of children on digital platforms is imperative. On the other hand, children also have a right to access information and enjoy communication on digital platforms. As such, digital platforms are a significant source of tension between the need for protection of children's privacy and the need for children to access information. Digital platforms develop their own standards and terms of service for their services that children and other users use. These standards and terms direct how digital platforms collect and utilise/process user data including children's data. The nature and purpose of data collection and use may violate the privacy of children. Furthermore, while some terms of service of digital platforms require prior and verifiable parental consent for the collection and processing of children's personal information, such mechanisms may not adequately protect children's privacy. This is particularly so in cases where even with prior and verifiable parental consent, children's data may be processed in ways that end up violating their right to privacy.

This requires the right framework for children's privacy protection – one that does not stifle children's ability to access information and contribute to discourse in the society and yet ensures the collection of children's data in a way that complies with privacy laws. Digital platforms need to be regulated, supported, informed and trained to support, promote and safeguard children and young people's wellbeing. There is need for regulation, support, information and training to ensure, promote and safeguard the privacy of children and young people on digital platforms.

The Challenge

Data Science Law Lab and the Centre for Child Law, a research group and, a research centre respectively, within the Department of Private Law, University of Pretoria (UP), has partnered to crowdsource novel proposals aimed at protecting the privacy of children and young people on digital platforms. The best submissions will be practical, implementable, testable (i.e., using real life data), scalable, and user-friendly. Winning submissions must have direct applicability to stated challenges that the South African Information Regulator,

[Human Rights Commission], and other South African governmental agencies are actively working to overcome to protect the privacy of children and young people on digital platforms.

With this challenge, solvers are asked to prototype solutions that enable more effective public-private partnerships to facilitate or enhance operational cooperation among the private sector, communities and South African governmental agencies in the protection of the privacy of children on digital platforms. We call upon challenge solvers to help us develop clear, age-appropriate strategies and standards to protect the privacy of children on digital platforms and apps and to identify and counter new and existing trends and practices that adversely affect, violate and/or endanger children's privacy on digital platforms.

While any solution that directly addresses the above statement above are acceptable, we are specifically interested in solutions that integrate a public-private partnership to secure the privacy of children on digital platforms:

- Technical and policy solutions for use in securing, protecting and promoting the privacy of children on digital platforms, such as end-to-end encryption that recognises children's ages and works to protect children's data or algorithm that tests/assesses the child privacy levels of digital platforms' terms of service. Solutions that thoughtfully address both policy and technical aspects will be judged more favourably than solutions that only address one of these aspects.
- Tools to provide advice, support, self-assessment and training to help digital platforms work towards protecting the privacy of children and young people.

These solutions and tools may be in the form of standards, tools, benchmarks for best practices, guidelines, mechanisms for advice and support, etc. Solutions and tools may provide examples of good practice; offer generic and where possible, platform-specific templates and resources; and create an action plan which can be tailored to specific organisations to support the implementation of the requirements.

Solutions must:

- provide opportunity for stakeholder testing and for stakeholder feedback
- be user-friendly
- help digital platforms to be accountable by: allowing for users to measure their progress against the solutions [for example, if a set of standards is produced as a solution, digital platforms should be able to measure their progress against such standards or how well they are protecting children's privacy online]
- advise on 'how' and 'what' can be put in place to achieve them (i.e., the solutions).

Students' Solutions

Child privacy on digital platforms

Daniel Katongo Chola, PhD Candidate, University of Pretoria

Description of proposed solution

Integrate digital literacy and digital citizenship into formal education curricula. This will prepare children to build their highly needed 21st-century skills to function in every sphere of life as they protect their privacy and that of others.

How the proposed solution helps address the challenge

Children will formally learn how to protect their privacy, defend, and comprehend the ability to control how their data and devices are used. Children will develop and acquire skills, knowledge, and the right norms of behaviour for using technology responsibly and ethically, thereby protecting themselves and other users online and offline.

Novelty or originality of the idea

Integration of both digital literacy and digital citizenship will produce results intended to protect the child as digital literacy empowers individuals to critically evaluate online content, identify misinformation, and protect their personal information. In contrast, digital citizenship will prepare them for safe, responsible, and ethical use of digital tools and technologies. For now, there is weak formal education given to children on the responsible and ethical use of digital platforms and tools. Online use is left to chance depending on access, expression, openness, and the child's innovation and creativity, jeopardizing the privacy and safety of the children as they are left to discover and experience independently. The benefits of formally educating the children on digital literacy and citizenship enable them to maximise and safely enjoy the five principles of expression, access, openness, innovation, and privacy as digital rights responsibly and ethically thereby alleviating pain for the children that may come with cybercrime and bullying.

What the solution is dependent on

- Department of Basic Education (DBE) of the South African Government, Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET), and South Africa Council for Educators (SACE) in this case to ensure teacher orientation on digital literacy and digital citizenship content and guidelines.
- Human Rights Commission
- UNESCO and UNICEF on guidelines on global digital citizenship.

Mankaleme Ramokgola, Masters' student, University of Pretoria

Description of proposed solution

Develop a Software or Generative AI tool e.g. "Save-A-Child"; that enables parental control e.g. parental notification/alert the moment a transgression is committed and create safe online platforms, age filters for appropriate age-based content online.

How the proposed solution helps address the challenge

It will assist parents to set up alerts to track where the information e.g. photos, videos etc. appears, the person who shared the content, monitor responses and evaluate the website or site and determine if the content shared is appropriate or altered e.g. using deep fake for the interest of the child as well as protection of child's data. The tool or software can be used as educational tool for teaching children, adults, and teachers, how to prevent the dissemination of harmful content involving children and provide online safety tips. The tool can assist with minimizing cybersecurity issues and threats, cyberbullying and digital kidnapping. It will assist parents to familiarize themselves with the privacy policies, copyright of the sites, audience and option to set passwords and hide the content from search algorithm.

Novelty or originality of the idea

South Africa's Children's Act 38 of 2005, which is aimed at protecting children's including the right to privacy and also to protect children from exploitation and abuse. 2. Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA), Children are regarded as a vulnerable group, therefore additional caution is required when handling data that involves children. Permission must be obtained from the parents or guardian before processing any data involving minor children. 3. Cybercrimes and Cybersecurity Act 19 of 2020, it prevents the dissemination of harmful content involving children. Therefore, exploitation, cyberbullying are regarded as cybercrimes that can harm children and are not permitted. This tool is innovative and will solve most challenges posed by the above-mentioned Acts or legislation. It can also regulate children privacy online and their personal information. The tool has more benefits and will add value to the child privacy and protection. It will force content creators to obtain consent before collecting data from children and respect children's rights. It can serve as a tracking device, in South Africa children are kidnapped daily this can help minimize the risks.

What the solution is dependent on

- The availability of resources and purchase license where necessary/applicable
- High performance and computing are required for the success of the proposed solution.
- Ethical considerations.

- Run rigorous testing

Paul Apeh, Master's Student, University of Bradford, UK

Description of proposed solution

Develop an AI-powered tool that can automatically detect and blur or remove personal information (e.g., faces, names, locations) from photos and videos children share on social media platforms to prevent oversharing. To take it a step further, the privacy score algorithm will be integrated into the same tool. In addition to analysing individual pieces of content, the algorithm would consider factors such as the social media platform's overall data collection practices, security measures, and age-appropriate features. Based on these factors, the algorithm would generate a "privacy score" for each platform, ranging from very child-friendly to potentially risky.

This score could be displayed alongside the AI-powered content analysis results, giving children and parents a clear overview of the privacy implications of sharing on different platforms.

How the proposed solution helps address the challenge

The proposed AI-powered tool with integrated privacy scoring addresses the challenge of protecting children's privacy on social media platforms through proactive content filtering, real-time privacy guidance, and comprehensive privacy assessment. By automatically detecting and removing personal information from photos and videos before they are posted, the tool prevents accidental oversharing by children, reducing the risk of sensitive data exposure. The tool provides

immediate, context-specific feedback to children about the privacy implications of their shared content, helping them develop better digital literacy skills and make informed decisions about their online privacy. The privacy score algorithm evaluates the overall child-friendliness of different social media platforms, considering factors such as data collection practices, security measures, and age-appropriate design, giving children and parents a holistic view of the associated privacy risks. With clear, comparative privacy ratings, the tool empowers children and families to make informed decisions about which social media services to use and how to adjust their privacy settings and sharing behaviours. By publicly scoring and comparing the child-friendliness of different platforms, the tool incentivizes companies to improve their privacy practices and compete on the basis of protecting children's data, potentially driving industry-wide adoption of stronger privacy safeguards and more age-appropriate design.

Novelty or originality of the idea

The proposed AI-powered tool with integrated privacy scoring offers innovative features that address the problem of protecting children's privacy on social media more comprehensively and effectively than existing solutions. Firstly, the proactive content filtering using advanced AI techniques like facial recognition, object detection, and natural

language processing is a novel approach to preventing accidental oversharing. By leveraging cutting-edge AI algorithms, our tool can automatically identify and remove a wide range of personal information in real-time, providing a more robust and efficient solution to unintended data exposure.

Secondly, the integration of a privacy score algorithm that evaluates the overall child-friendliness of different social media platforms is a unique and valuable addition. By providing a holistic, data-driven assessment of each platform's privacy practices, security measures, and age-appropriate design, our tool empowers users to make more informed decisions about which platforms to use and how to navigate them safely. Finally, the public scoring and comparison of platforms' child-friendliness is an innovative approach to driving industry-wide change. By making these ratings visible and accessible, our tool creates a powerful incentive for social media companies to prioritize child privacy and compete on the basis of protecting children's data, potentially leading to wider adoption of stronger privacy safeguards and more age-appropriate design.

What the solution is dependent on

The success of the proposed AI-powered tool with integrated privacy scoring depends on several key requirements and partnerships.

1. Access to detailed information about each platform's data collection, use, and retention policies is necessary to effectively analyse and score their privacy practices.
2. Collaboration with child privacy experts from academia, advocacy groups, and regulatory bodies is essential to ensuring the comprehensiveness, accuracy, and alignment of the privacy scoring algorithm with best practices in child online protection.
3. Implementing the proactive content filtering feature requires significant computational resources and expertise in AI technologies like computer vision, natural language processing, and machine learning.
4. Extensive user testing and feedback, potentially involving partnerships with schools, community organisations, or online parent groups, is crucial to ensuring the tool's user-friendliness, effectiveness, and cultural appropriateness for children and families from diverse backgrounds.
5. Developing and maintaining a sophisticated AI tool with ongoing data analysis and platform scoring necessitates substantial financial resources, which may be secured through grants, sponsorships, or partnerships with educational institutions or child advocacy groups.
6. A long-term sustainability plan is also necessary to ensure the tool's continuous operation and evolution alongside changing social media platforms and privacy challenges. Proactively identifying and addressing these dependencies increases the likelihood of successful implementation and goal achievement.

Obakeng Ncube, Masters' student, University of Pretoria

Description of proposed solution

Child privacy on digital platforms presents issues that, if not addressed carefully, could undermine trust in emerging technology. Furthermore, in an era of rising data collection and use, child privacy protection is more essential than ever, because digital tools not only help society, but policy frameworks, the state and other stakeholders must also protect privacy while allowing for innovation.

How the proposed solution helps address the challenge

- a) I propose the following solutions to address the challenge of child privacy on digital platforms: The state should establish and implement a policy framework to protect child privacy on digital platforms. This may necessitate the creation of new laws, such as data protection laws, that include appropriate provisions for the processing of personal information relating to children, ensuring that such child personal information is processed in a fair, lawful, transparent, and compatible manner with the purpose for which it was collected.
- b) Digital literacy should be taught from an early age. Only through such digital literacy can children and young people properly understand their right to privacy in their personal capacities, as well as understand the implications for them now and in the future.
- c) Private sector individuals should implement rules consistent with South African legislation and other international law guidance on the right to privacy. Such rules should be easily accessible and clear, addressing processes such as data collecting, retention, and preservation; proper online advertising to children; and ownership and removal of user-generated content.
- d) Parents and guardians should be thoughtful and deliberate in their approaches to exercising appropriate supervision over the right to privacy, avoiding unreasonably restricting the right. This may help parents and guardians ensure that the child's rights, such as freedom of expression, participation, and development, are not jeopardized or infringed in the name of adult respect. The advancement of privacy-protecting technologies, as well as online platforms and services, should be encouraged and supported.

Novelty or originality of the idea

The solutions mentioned above are fundamental considering that they protect children from major concerns such as identity theft and the online predators who can exploit personal information for cyberbullying, stalking, ransomware, or even abduction. This will

help children secure their identity, reputation, and safety. and wellbeing. Without privacy online, children may divulge too much personal information about themselves or others, which hackers, scammers, predators, or cyberbullies could use against them. Child privacy on digital platforms can be jeopardized not just by the information they choose to publish about themselves, but also by others sharing or gathering information, such as contact information or photographs of those children.

What the solution is dependent on

To ensure proper implementation of solutions have provided:

- a. Public-Private collaborative process.
- b. Enable, connect, and expand small-scale, localised digital education project.
- c. Proper training of children and parents on how digital platforms without risky the child privacy.
- d. Prioritise digital inclusion in education.
- e. Transform teacher's education to meet the demands of digital education.
- f. Establish a policy and planning for child privacy on digital platform.

Qudisiyah Vahed, Masters' student, University of Pretoria

Description of proposed solution

This solution firstly requires social media users to complete a self-assessment questionnaire about the content they are posting before posting on a social media platform. After the user posts their content, the content is evaluated by an AI assistant for any prohibited activities. The AI flags content and gives it back to the user to evaluate, the AI then states how the user can improve the post to comply with the child safety rules and regulations. After this the content is approved by the AI and posted and checked by a human moderator.

How the proposed solution helps address the challenge

This solution addresses the challenge by providing a policy-based and technological-based solution as well as tools for users. This solution relies on forming new rules and regulations that are based on international benchmarks for the ethical use of social media particularly related to child online safety. Furthermore, the solution proposes ways that these rules and regulations can be implemented on social media platforms. From this, records can be kept on a social media platforms compliance to the proposed rules and regulations. Recording the compliance of a social media platforms to the rules and regulations creates an opportunity for users to judge the platform and creates accountability.

Novelty or originality of the idea

The proposed solution informs users on basic child privacy and safety issues and how to protect children online. Users are provided with tools to identify possible child safety violations and are given the opportunity for rectify any possible violations in their own capacity. Furthermore, the proposed solution provides a way to categorize and identify the safety of media channels for children. This data can be relayed to users to inform them on the safety of particular social media channels. Social media platforms can then be judged by users and given scores/badges on their safety which will incentivize the social media platform to create a safer space for young users.

What the solution is dependent on

The innovative aspects of my proposed solution lie in its holistic and integrated approach to safeguarding children's digital privacy, combining advanced technologies with strategic partnerships and comprehensive education.

1. Introducing age-aware encryption protocols that automatically adjust based on the user's age ensures enhanced privacy tailored to children's needs. This goes beyond traditional data protection methods by dynamically adapting security measures, addressing the specific vulnerabilities of young users. The success of

age-appropriate content filtering technologies on platforms like Netflix and YouTube Kids demonstrates the feasibility of such solutions.

2. Utilizing biometric verification, two-factor authentication, and blockchain for parental consent mechanisms significantly improves the reliability and traceability of consent. This innovation addresses the common issue of easily circumvented consent processes, ensuring genuine parental involvement.
3. Implementing AI-driven privacy auditing tools offers real-time monitoring and immediate alerts for potential privacy violations, ensuring ongoing compliance and rapid response to threats, which is a significant improvement over periodic audit. Also, developing algorithms to assess and rate digital platforms' privacy policies will help ensure compliance with privacy standards. assessments.
4. Establishing a regulatory sandbox for public-private collaboration allows for the testing and refinement of privacy protection technologies and policies in a controlled environment. This innovative framework ensures that solutions are practical, effective, and ready for broader application.

Sibabalwe Nongwana Masters' student, University of Pretoria

Description of proposed solution

The rapid expansion of digital technologies has profoundly reshaped children's lives, integrating online activities into their daily routines for education, entertainment, and social interaction. However, this digital immersion poses significant risks to children's privacy and safety. To safeguard children's digital privacy, I propose a comprehensive approach that includes public-private partnerships, technical innovations, policy reforms, and educational initiatives. This solution leverages global best practices and adapts them to local contexts to create a robust framework protecting children's privacy while allowing safe digital exploration. Key elements include age-aware encryption, verifiable parental consent systems, real-time privacy monitoring tools, and community education programs, all aimed at ensuring minimal data collection and robust data protection.

How the proposed solution helps address the challenge

My proposed solution addresses the challenge of child privacy online through a multifaceted approach that tackles the core issues of data collection, parental consent, and digital literacy.

1. By implementing age-aware encryption and contextual data collection strategies, the solution ensures that only the necessary data is collected from children. This minimizes the risk of data misuse and enhances data protection.
2. The solution improves verifiable parental consent systems using advanced technologies like biometric verification and two-factor authentication. This ensures that consent is genuine and traceable, thus preventing unauthorized data collection.
3. Continuous privacy auditing tools powered by AI and machine learning allow for real-time monitoring of digital platforms. This helps in quickly identifying and addressing potential privacy violations, ensuring ongoing compliance with privacy standards.
4. Community and parental education programs, along with training for digital platform employees, raise awareness about digital privacy risks and best practices. This empowers parents, children, and industry professionals to better protect children's online privacy.
5. Establishing a regulatory sandbox and joint task forces fosters collaboration between government, industry, and civil society. This helps in developing and refining privacy protection technologies and policies, ensuring that they are practical and effective. A multi-stakeholder task force would oversee the sandbox, develop test cases, and analyze results to inform broader policy recommendations.

The success of regulatory sandboxes in the UK and Singapore for fintech innovation provides a model for this approach.

Novelty or originality of the idea

The innovative aspects of my proposed solution lie in its holistic and integrated approach to safeguarding children's digital privacy, combining advanced technologies with strategic partnerships and comprehensive education.

1. Introducing age-aware encryption protocols that automatically adjust based on the user's age ensures enhanced privacy tailored to children's needs. This goes beyond traditional data protection methods by dynamically adapting security measures, addressing the specific vulnerabilities of young users. The success of age-appropriate content filtering technologies on platforms like Netflix and YouTube Kids demonstrates the feasibility of such solutions.
2. Utilizing biometric verification, two-factor authentication, and blockchain for parental consent mechanisms significantly improves the reliability and traceability of consent. This innovation addresses the common issue of easily circumvented consent processes, ensuring genuine parental involvement.
3. Implementing AI-driven privacy auditing tools offers real-time monitoring and immediate alerts for potential privacy violations, ensuring ongoing compliance and rapid response to threats, which is a significant improvement over periodic audit. Also, developing algorithms to assess and rate digital platforms' privacy policies will help ensure compliance with privacy standards. assessments.
3. Establishing a regulatory sandbox for public-private collaboration allows for the testing and refinement of privacy protection technologies and policies in a controlled environment. This innovative framework ensures that solutions are practical, effective, and ready for broader application.
4. Integrating community and parental education programs with industry training creates a well-informed user base and workforce. This addresses the lack of awareness and knowledge, empowering users to protect children's privacy actively.

What the solution is dependent on

1. Strong partnerships between South African government agencies, digital platforms, civil society organizations, and child advocacy groups are essential. These collaborations will facilitate the creation and operation of a regulatory sandbox and the development of effective policies and guidelines tailored to local needs.
2. Access to cutting-edge technologies such as biometric verification, two-factor authentication, blockchain, AI, and machine learning is crucial. These technologies

are needed to develop robust parental consent systems, real-time privacy monitoring tools, and age-aware encryption protocols.

3. Engaging data scientists, cybersecurity experts, and legal professionals is necessary to design, implement, and maintain the technical solutions. Their expertise will ensure that the algorithms and systems developed are effective and compliant with privacy standards, including the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA).
4. Securing adequate funding and resources is vital for the development, testing, and scaling of the proposed solutions. This includes investments in technology infrastructure, pilot programs, and educational initiatives. An estimated budget of ZAR 70 million over three years is required for these activities.
5. Strong support from regulatory bodies such as the Information Regulator is required to enforce new policies and standards. This includes the development of comprehensive child privacy guidelines and accountability mechanisms under POPIA.
6. Collaborations with educational institutions and community organizations are essential for delivering digital literacy campaigns and training programs. These entities will help raise awareness and educate parents, children, and industry professionals about privacy risks and best practices, ensuring the solution's sustainability and effectiveness in the South African context.

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Africa, Law & [Emerging] Technologies Policy Hackathon 2024: Child Privacy

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1. Solution Overview

Child privacy in South Africa is regulated by 3 main laws which are aimed at protecting children, their privacy on line and their personal information.

- a. Children's Act 38 of 2005, which is aimed at protecting children's including the right to privacy and also to protect children from exploitation and abuse.
- b. Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA), Children are regarded as a vulnerable group, therefore additional caution is required when handling data that involves children. Permission must be obtained from the parents or guardian before processing any data involving minor children.
- c. Cybercrimes and Cybersecurity Act 19 of 2020, it prevents the dissemination of harmful content involving children. Therefore, exploitation, cyberbullying is regarded as cybercrimes that can harm children and are not permitted.

2. Solutions to protect Children online

2.1 Digital literacy: Educating parents, children, guardians and caregivers about child privacy online, cybersecurity, implications and the consequences thereof. This should be part of the curriculum and educational programs. This should also include online safety tips, how to prevent the dissemination of harmful content involving children. How to use the internet in a responsible manner and how privacy can be maintained.

2.2 Create more safe online platforms and provide online safety tips: When this is done it should include age filters for appropriate age-based content online, advertisements that cater for kids and safe websites that are constantly monitored. It should notify the parent, caregiver and guardian if harmful content has been shared.

2.3 Framework, new policies and guidelines: Strict enforcement of legislation. The laws to protect children are there but the issue is the enforcement thereof because even our police are not well trained to understand what the laws mean and how it should be enforced. We also need more strict penalties for those found in contravention of any law that involves the protection of children.

2.4 Technology-based solutions: These solutions should be aimed at creating software that enable parental control for example, parental notification the moment a

transgression is committed. It offers, age restrictions, authentications and registrations on the platform. It is child friendly solution which will give parents, caregivers and guardians peace of mind and also protect the child privacy.

3. Value Proposition

It will definitely add value and solve online child privacy issues in South Africa and globally.

3.1 What aspect of the challenge does your solution address?

The proposed solution addresses the identity and security of a child online. It will have a generative AI solution that will detect deep fake.

3.2 What stakeholders are involved in your solution? Which specific stakeholder(s) would benefit most from your solution?

- a) Parents, Guardians, Caregivers and Children
- b) Government, Department of Higher Education
- c) Companies
- d) NGOs especially those dealing with vulnerable children
- e) Private entities
- f) Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), e.g. Department of Higher Education (Early Childhood Education).

3.3 What difference would your solution make for the target end user?

It will first bring awareness or digital literacy that leads to knowledge and knowledge is power. Parents, guardians, caregivers and children will know how to govern content online. They will know what to share, where to share and what content to consume. Firstly, for children, it will enhance online safety, meaning it will be safeguarding tool. Content Filtering, which will protect children from exposure to inappropriate or harmful content and safe communication which ensures that interactions and communications online are monitored to prevent cyberbullying, harassment, and contact with potential predators. It will also increase privacy awareness and digital experience although be controlled. Secondly, for parents, caregivers, guardians it will give them opportunity to

consent, have access to what their children are doing online and be able to delete. Basically, it enhances parental control and guidance, which lead to peace of mind because they will receive activity alerts. Overall, it enhances security, empowerment etc.

4. Potential Application

Our approach to the problem of children privacy will be relevant to the different stakeholders and possible instances listed below:

4.1 To protect children's privacy on digital platforms, the state ought to create and put into effect a policy framework. This might call for the enactment of new legislation, like data protection laws, that include suitable guidelines for processing child personal information and guarantee that it is handled fairly, legally, transparently, and in a way that is compatible with the reason it was gathered. For instance, new laws tailored to the usage of artificial intelligence and digital platforms or settings should be put into place by the state. There are laws and policies that guarantee the creation and protection of child privacy laws when developing digital platforms.

4.2 Individuals in the private sector ought to enact regulations that are compliant with international law guidelines on privacy rights as well as South African legislation. The regulations, which cover topics including data collection, preservation, and retention; appropriate online advertising to minors; and ownership and removal of user-generated content, need to be simple to find and understand.

4.3 Teaching digital literacy at an early age is important. Children and young people may only fully comprehend their right to privacy in their personal capacities and the ramifications for them now and in the future through such digital literacy. Children should be taught, for instance, how to utilize digital platforms and what kind of information they can publish online. Which information must be approved by their parents or guardians before being shared or posted? This will stop young children from providing information on internet networks that could compromise their privacy.

4.4 Parents and guardians should be thoughtful and deliberate in their approaches to exercising appropriate supervision over the right to privacy, avoiding unreasonably

restricting the right. Parents and guardians ensure that the child's rights, such as freedom of expression, participation, and development, are not jeopardized or infringed in the name of adult respect. For example, parents or guardians may be educated about what to post or share on an online platform concerning child information.

4.5 It is important to promote and assist in the development of online platforms and services, as well as privacy-preserving technologies. These need to be made with children in mind, considering how they would utilize the gadgets. Devices should, for instance, be equipped with software or an application that forbids the publication or sharing of any data that violates the privacy of children. Similarly, on devices lacking this software or program, the website should indicate that certain data was published or posted on social media, Google, etc. As a result, this information violates children's privacy and should suggest consequences for the offending behavior.

The solutions I have provided above are important because they protect children against serious threats, including identity theft and online predators that can use personal information for cyberbullying, stalking, ransomware, or even abduction. This will help children to protect their identity, reputation, safety, and well-being. Without online privacy, children may reveal too much information about themselves or others that can be used against them by hackers, scammers, predators, or cyberbullies. Child privacy on a digital platform can be compromised not only by the information they choose to share about themselves but also by others sharing or even gathering information such as contact information or pictures of those children. This solution is better because we can identify the data that is being posted on social media that violates child privacy and recommend a suitable punishment for that particular violation. Despite the fact that this solution might make a huge contribution to child privacy protection, we have identified that there are also weaknesses:

a. Lack of collaboration

Stakeholders might not work effectively together. For this proposed solution to effectively work and produce the anticipated outcome, all the stakeholders must come to the party. However, due to differences, some stakeholders might not want to compromise, and implementation of the idea might be one of the weaknesses.

b. User awareness and approval

Different children comprehend privacy and the risks associated with using the internet differently. Another weakness might be designing child-friendly interfaces and rules, as well as making sure children could give informed permission when necessary.

5. Assumptions and limitations

5.1 Assumptions and limitations for finding solution

A number of fundamental assumptions and factors must be taken into account while creating solutions for child privacy in order to guarantee successful complaint design. These assumptions influence how services and technologies that protect children online are developed. The following are the limitations and assumptions we encountered as a team:

5.1.1 Locating a relevant source

It's effective to use moderation and content screening in order to protect kids from objectionable or harmful content. The use of technology and services for content moderation that are intended to detect and eliminate content that is unsuitable for children has been problematic for our team when we were formulating solutions.

5.1.2 Parental approval and participation

In order to monitor and secure their children's internet activity, parents or guardians are crucial. Another concern was putting in place procedures to include guardians or parents in the permission process, especially for processing sensitive data or younger children.

5.2 Assumptions and limitation for prototype

Designing a conceptual model or preliminary version of a solution that prioritizes safeguarding children's online privacy is the first step in developing a prototype to address child privacy challenges. The following were the assumptions and constraints we encountered when creating a prototype:

5.2.1 Research and gathering data

It was difficult to state the precise issue of child privacy in a clear and concise manner. We did know whether we ought to concentrate on content evaluation, consent management, and age verification. Do an in-depth study on pertinent child privacy legislation and best practices (such as POPIA, the Children Act, the Constitution of 1996, etc.). Another problem was gathering criteria based on user demands (learning

institutions, parents/guardians, and children) as well as technology viability and regulatory compliance.

5.2.2 Identifying important features and functionality

It was difficult for the team to determine what features the prototype needed to have in order to properly handle the stated child privacy issue. Age verification systems, tools for managing permission, the ability to moderate content and instructional materials are a few examples of features.

5.2.3 Choose technologies and APIs

It was difficult to select the right technologies and APIs (such as programming languages, frameworks, third-party APIs for content moderation or age verification) based on the specifications of our prototype.

5.2.4 Designing the prototype

Make sure that the prototype's development process and architecture incorporate privacy-by-design concepts. This covers user-centric privacy settings, data minimization, and safe data management procedures. Begin constructing the prototype with the chosen technologies and APIs. Prioritize the implementation of essential features and the integration of data processing, security protocols, and privacy controls.

6.1 Operational Requirement

Software development must address child privacy issues in a number of ways, including through the use of programs, APIs, and data considerations. A brief overview of what is required is as follows: To write and manage your code, use a text editor or an Integrated Development Environment (IDE). Eclipse, PyCharm, IntelliJ IDEA, Visual Studio Code, and others are a few examples. Put in place a Git-style version control system. This will enable you to efficiently handle codebase changes. A database management system (DBMS) might be required to store and manage data securely, depending on the needs of your application. In order to abide with privacy rules and best practices, you would normally combine several APIs and services, even though there might not be any separate services specifically designed to protect children's privacy.

The following are some examples of APIs and services to be considered: APIs that ascertain a user's age or whether they are a minor. Services or APIs that help create privacy rules that comply. APIs that manage user consent for actions related to data processing. APIs that authenticate users, which may assist in guaranteeing compliance to age-related laws. APIs that offer tools or updates to help you comply with changing privacy laws, like the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, Protection of Personal Information Act, 4 of 2013 (POPIA), Children's Act 38 of 2005, Regulations relating to the Protection of Personal Information, Cybercrime Act 19 of 2020, etc. You may also integrate with other third-party APIs for extra features like analytics, user administration, or content filtering, depending on the functions of your application. Make sure you manage and preserve user data safely and in accordance with all applicable laws and rules protecting the privacy of minors. This covers sensitive data and personally identifiable information (PII). Make sure your terms of service and privacy policies are crystal clear and specify how you will manage user data, particularly child-related data.

7.1 Implementation Requirements

This is child and user friendly interface based solution, wherein users can lodge a complain, have chatbot embedded to provide feedback. The potential end-user agency or company should put measures in place, e.g. internet, Data Protection, POPIA laws and regulations. This requires a multi-faceted approach. Budget to purchase a license or subscribe. They should have personnel to work full-time on this solution. Be able to block unauthorized users and content that is harmful to children. Potential end-user should consider the following:

- 7.1.1 Legal and regulatory compliance aspect: comply with the laws, copyright of the solution e.g. GDPR. Registration, authentication and age verification mechanisms should be in place.
- 7.1.2 Security Measures: run frequent audits to identify and mitigate risks
- 7.1.3 Data Protection and Privacy: be able to anonymize and de-identify personal data wherever possible to protect children's identities. Encryption is important. Ensure that access to children's data is restricted to authorized personnel and that robust authentication mechanisms are in place.

7.1.4 Parental Controls and Consent: mechanisms on how parents can give consent and manage their children's data. The end user to be able to monitor and control children's activities and data usage within the software.

8. Next Steps

If we were given enough time, we would produce a quality work, prototype, model or algorithm, tested by all stakeholders.

9. Estimated Budget

Creating a cost structure for a software development project involves breaking down the budget which differs from developer to developer, across various phases of the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC). Here's a sample cost structure with a total project budget of 1 million South African Rands (ZAR). This is just an estimation not real figures, we projecting it to be less.

Sample Cost Structure for a Software Development Project

Total Project Budget: R1,000,000

9.1 Planning and Requirements Gathering (10%)

Activities: Initial meetings, requirement gathering, feasibility study, project planning.

- Estimated Cost: R100,000

9.2 System Design (15%)

Activities: Creating design specifications, system architecture, UI/UX design.

- Estimated Cost: R150,000

9.3 Development (40%)

Activities: Actual coding, software construction, unit testing.

- Estimated Cost: R400,000

9.4 Testing (20%)

Activities: Integration testing, system testing, user acceptance testing, bug fixing.

- Estimated Cost: R200,000

9.5 Deployment (5%)

Activities: Deployment to production environment, training, documentation.

- Estimated Cost: R50,000

9.6 Maintenance and Support (10%)

Activities: Ongoing support, updates, and maintenance post-deployment.

- Estimated Cost: R100,000

Detailed Breakdown

Planning and Requirements Gathering

- Project Manager: R60,000
- Business Analyst: R40,000

System Design

- System Architect: R80,000
- UI/UX Designer: R50,000
- Documentation: R20,000

Development

- Front-end Developers: R150,000
- Back-end Developers: R200,000
- Database Developers: R50,000

Testing

- Testers: R150,000
- Automated Testing Tools: R30,000
- Bug Fixing: R20,000

Deployment

- Deployment Specialist: R30,000
- Training and Documentation: R20,000

Maintenance and Support

- Support Team: R70,000
- Updates and Patches: R30,000

Summary

- Planning and Requirements Gathering: R100,000
- System Design: R150,000
- Deployment: R400,000
- Testing: R200,000
- Deployment: R50,000
- Maintenance and Support: R100,000

This structure ensures that all phases of the SDLC are adequately funded, helping to ensure the project's success. Adjustments can be made based on the specific requirements and complexity of the project.

Experts' Discourse

Child privacy on digital platforms

- **Mr Bibitayo Ojo, DataPro Limited**
- **Ms Adaobi Olaye, Data Protection Services Professionals**
- **Joshua Kitili, Centre for Intellectual Property and Information Technology
Law, Strathmore University, Kenya**
- **Ms Ifeoluwa Ebiseni, Flutterwave**

SAFEGUARDING CHILDREN'S ONLINE PRIVACY IN AFRICA'S DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM

Bibitayo Ojo

ABOUT THE DISCUSSION

This discussion addresses the urgent need to safeguard children's online privacy and data in this era of evolving technologies. I will examine the multifaceted challenges faced by African children, including exposure to cyberbullying, exploitation, and data breaches, often aggravated by limited digital literacy.

STATISTICS OF NETIZEN

- 346 million children in Africa are online (ITU, 2022)
- 1 in 3 internet users worldwide is a child (UNICEF, 2020)
- 71% of children online have experienced cyberbullying (ITU, 2022)

4 C RISKS

CONTACT

CONTENT

CONDUCT

CONTRACT

SHORTCOMINGS OF EXISTING SOLUTIONS

GAPS

1 Age gating can be boycotted

2 Privacy by design is highly risky

3 Balance is data limitation and storage

Digital Literacy

- Digital literacy empowers individuals with the knowledge, skills, and confidence to navigate and thrive in a rapidly evolving technological landscape. It enables them to effectively adapt to the transformative impact of computers and digital tools, harnessing these changes to enhance their personal and professional lives in meaningful ways

Examples:

- Africa Digital Literacy Scheme [Abuja]
- Australian Government's eSafety Information Hub (Office of the Australian Information Commissioner)

Ms Adaobi Olaye, Data Protection Services Professionals

Africa, Law & Emerging Technologies POLICY HACKATHON

CHILD PRIVACY SOLUTIONS: KIDTAP

PROBLEM

The Right

Global Privacy Regulations generally recognise that children under the ages of 18 years (Nigerian Data Protection Act, 2023; 16 years under the Children's Online Privacy Protection Act (COPPA)) and in some member states of the EU minors under 13 years reserve the right to have their personal data specifically protected.

Africa, Law & Emerging Technologies POLICY HACKATHON

CHILD PRIVACY SOLUTIONS: KIDTAP

PROBLEM

Incidents

Facebook-Cambridge Analytic (2018):
Although not exclusively about children, this scandal highlighted how personal data, including that of minors, was harvested & used without proper consent, raising concerns about privacy and data protection.

Google's YouTube Violations (2019):
The Federal Trade Commission (FTC) fined Google \$170 million for violating COPPA by collecting personal data from children under 13 on YouTube without proper consent.

TikTok Data Collection Concerns (2020):
TikTok faced scrutiny for its data collection practices, including the collection of data from minors, leading to investigations and regulatory actions in various countries, including the U.S. and the EU.

Children's App Privacy Issues (Various):
Numerous apps designed for children have been found to mishandle data, such as by tracking location or collecting personal information without adequate parental consent, leading to legal actions & fines. These incidents underscore the importance of stringent privacy protection and compliance with legal standards to safeguard children's personal information.

Several notable incidents involving the infringement of child privacy rights have occurred globally

SOLUTIONS

INNOVATION DRIVEN INITIATIVES

Create an add-on solution that effectively and proactively collects, categorises & prompts additional safeguards to be implemented with respect to children's privacy while yet providing a positive user experience.

MULTI-LAYER AGE VERIFICATION PROCESS

Implement age verification before and during the user experience to ensure that the solution is appropriate for the child's age group.

PARENTAL CONTROLS

Design features that allow parents to manage and monitor their child's use of the add-on. This could include parental dashboards, consent management, and activity monitoring. For Minors, Consent Management to ensure data minimisation is implemented.

INTERFACE ADAPTABILITY

Using an adaptive user interface (UI) to enhance child privacy protection involves designing the UI to dynamically adjust based on contextual cues and user behavior, with a strong focus on safeguarding children's personal information and online activities. This can be achieved through using robust parental control features, age-appropriate content, targeted user education.

DESIGN FOR ACCESSIBILITY

Ensure the UI is accessible to children with diverse needs, including those with disabilities.

Cross-Platform Frameworks: Use frameworks like React Native or Flutter for a consistent experience across iOS and Android.

Privacy-focused Design: Implement features like anonymous login options, minimal data sharing, and clear privacy notices.

DESIGN FOR ADAPTABILITY TO ANDROID, IOS SETTINGS & APP STORE COMPLIANCE

Ensure the add-on meets both Apple App Store and Google Play Store policies. Device manufacturers can also be encouraged to incorporate into user settings from the jump.

Cross-Platform Frameworks: Use frameworks like React Native or Flutter for a consistent experience across iOS & Android.

Privacy-focused Design: Implement features like anonymous login options, minimal data sharing, and clear privacy notices.

SOLUTIONS

POLICY DRIVEN INITIATIVES

1

Statutory review and amendment to existing regulatory framework.

2

Statutory amendment to include a reclassification & categorisation of children personal data

3

Statutory guidance required to develop child privacy led messaging in Marketing campaigns to adequately assure minors and their legal proxies of their rights, obligations and responsibilities (this may also require review of broadcasting and online media regulation)

THANK YOU!

? +
QUESTIONS?

ADAABI OLAYE

Parental Responsibility in Fortifying Children's Privacy

Joshua Kitili

Strathmore University
Centre for Intellectual Property and
Information Technology Law

Problem Statement

- The African Union notes that digital access in Africa is rapidly expanding, with many new users being children under 18. Globally, 1 in 3 internet users is a child, and over 175,000 children go online for the first time each day.
- In Africa, an estimated 40% of youth aged 15-24 have internet access. As more children connect to the digital world, the associated risks they face online have also increased.
- Children interact with various digital technologies such as virtual assistants, wearable devices, smartphones, and interactive toys, which influence their childhood positively and negatively.

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Digital Risks Children may encounter

- **Cyberbullying-** This may be perpetrated by and among the children themselves.
- **Exposure to Inappropriate Content** which may include discriminatory , hateful, sexual and violent expressions.
- **Sexual risks and Exploitation**
- **Posting private information-** They may not yet understand social boundaries hence share private information not meant for the public.

Parental Responsibility in Children's Privacy

- Parental responsibility encompasses a wide range of roles, including providing guardianship, care, necessary support, and maintaining communication with the child.
- It should be carried out with steadfast dedication to the child's best interests, a fundamental principle that supports the protection and promotion of children's rights.
- Parental responsibility can also potentially limit a child's autonomy, making it crucial to balance the two to avoid hindering the child's development.

Role of Parents in Privacy Regulation

- Parents have the right to exercise reasonable supervision over the behaviour of their children and may also consent to the processing of their children's data. For instance the Protection of Personal Information Act 2013 requires consent from a competent person (someone with parental responsibility as per the children's Act) where the data subject is a child.
- Some suggested ways of verifying the consent of parents include:
 - The provision of passport or ID copy via e-mail
 - The provision of a consent or authorisation letter signed via email.
 - Processing of online orders through a parent's credit card
 - Parents consent is authorized via telephone

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Parents' actions that compromise children's privacy

- **Sharenting-** This is where a parent may continually post images, videos and information about their child/children on the internet without their consent. Oversharing a child's personal data could potentially expose the child to online harms such as cyberbullying and unsolicited attention by online predators.
- **Failure to read privacy policies-**Not reading and grasping the privacy policies of apps and services used by children could expose the personal data shared to misuse especially if the privacy policy is not robust
- **Failure to educate children on privacy -**By educating children about potential risks and teaching them to navigate the digital world responsibly, parents and schools can empower them to make informed decisions and safeguard their digital privacy.
- **Inadequate Monitoring-**To mitigate digital risks for children, parents can use parental controls and monitoring tools to block inappropriate content, limit screen time, and monitor online interactions.
- **Failure to review and manage app permissions-**Reviewing and managing app permissions limit access to a child's personal data, such as location, contacts, and photos.

Technical Solutions

- To limit sharenting, privacy settings may be improved to limit who can view and interact with the shared content. This may include:
 - Visibility settings for various users.
 - Integrating a consent form before sharing information relating to a child.
 - Integrate tools that anonymise images or videos of children hence removing identifiable features.
- User-friendly privacy policies highlighting key points in summary form at the point of an app's first use may be integrated to ensure parents familiarize themselves.
- Parental guidance tools like educational videos or tips can be integrated to enable parents educate their children about privacy. Additionally, developing simple educational modules focused on privacy protection will educate children.
- Concerning parental control and monitoring, implementing an alert system that notifies parents of unusual activities such as interaction with strangers will enhance a child's safety.
- Regarding App permissions, tools can be created that allow parents to review and manage all the app permissions granted and modify them as they deem fit.

Policy Solutions-Comparative Assessment

- **US Children's Online Privacy Protection Act**-The legislation requires notifying parents about data practices, obtaining verifiable parental consent for processing children's personal information, and allowing parents to control how their child's data is used and to limit further processing. It also mandates parental access to their child's data, advocates for data minimization by collecting only what is necessary, and requires implementing measures to ensure the security, integrity, and confidentiality of children's personal information.
- **UK Code of Practice to protect children's privacy online**-It is targeted at those involved in designing, developing, or offering online services such as apps, connected toys, social media platforms, online games, educational websites, and streaming services. The main principle of the Code is that service providers must ensure high standards for default privacy settings on services and digital products accessible to children, prioritizing the best interests of the child.

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Policy Solutions-Comparative Assessment

- **OECD Guidelines for Digital Service Providers-**The Guidelines urge service providers to establish governance and accountability mechanisms that promote the best interests of the child when accessing their products and services.
- **Guidelines on Children's Data Protection in an Education Setting-** These guidelines are intended to help organizations and individuals in the education sector respect, protect, and fulfill children's data protection rights within the digital environment.

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The End

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Introduction

Protection of child privacy on digital platforms is one of the burning issues in this digital, global village, particularly with the increasing migration of information, access and communication tools to the internet.

Issues

- I
- Age Appropriation/ Verification for Children
- Parental Control and Data Access
- Further Processing/ Purpose Limitation
- Transparency
- Monitoring, Surveillance
- Profiling, Bias, Discrimination
- Trust, Safety Issues

Solutions

1. Age Appropriation/Verification Tool/ Policy:

Age verification tools pose certain threats to data subjects.

Utilising products that seek to balance this. - A facial age-estimation product (third party application)

- Computer vision
- ML tech
- Immediate deletion
- Liveness test to prevent spoofing
- Distinct from other verification tools

Additionally: In line with data privacy principles, this could be merged with an ongoing verification mechanism- Psychometric Age Estimation (use of behavioural pattern to determine age).
(- More research- stakeholder engagement)

****From a policy perspective: Propose amendment to regional and local legislations containing use of invasive, bias-prone age verification mechanisms.

Solutions

2. Parental Consent/ Controls:

Age verification tools pose certain threats to data subjects

- A parental mediation strategy to ensure children's safety in a digital age is the use of parental control tools.
- A review of the effectiveness of parental controls reveals mixed results: some uses of parental controls bring benefits, for example to children's safety, but others have no effect or limit children's opportunities, and some have adverse results, for example to family communication.- [Mariya Stoilova, Monica Bulger, Sonia Livingstone](#) (29 Oct 2023)

Proposed solution - A good approach would be to develop parental control embedded in the everyday mix of parental mediation practices in everyday family life.

- access control apps, similar to the authenticator apps used as 2FAs. These apps would embed training videos and manuals on how to achieve joint rule setting for parents and children.

Solutions

3. Working Groups and Self-Regulation by Industry Players- Stakeholder engagement (Proposal of child privacy specific rules and policies).

**Advertising sector has some form of self regulation- the Children Advertising Review Unit of the National Advertising Review Unit (CARU)

4. Privacy by Design and Default for applications designed for children/ applications that children have access to.

5. Illustrations, graphics and child-friendly privacy notices

Conclusion

(P.S: Trust, safety, content moderation cannot be strictly isolated from privacy in achieving a healthy digital environment for children)

Challenge: Data privacy in public health context

In collaboration with South African National Bioinformatics Institute, University of the Western Cape, South Africa

Participants *(in alphabetical order)*

- Kedir Hussein Abegaz, University of Pretoria
- Linomtha Gabada, University of Pretoria
- Tshepo Leso, Tshwane University of Technology
- Tshepo Mabelane, University of Pretoria
- Bonza Majozi, University of Pretoria
- Sandiso Mbulawa, University of Fort Hare
- Thandi Mpopo, University of Pretoria
- Xitshembhiso Russel Mulamula, Near East University
- Bothabo Ngwenya, University of Pretoria
- Juliet Rushambwe, University of Pretoria
- Nare Segole, University of Pretoria
- Atalia Shube, University of Pretoria
- Thapelo Andrew Sindane, University of Pretoria
- Mfundo Zwane, University of Cape Town

Finalists

- Bonza Majozi (Winner)
- Vukosi Majozi

Challenge Statement

Data privacy in public health context

Background

Advances in biotechnology, and in particular, next generation sequencing and ‘-omics’ has catapulted the use of these technologies within the realm of public health. The adoption of pathogen genomics by public health agencies has been pivotal for communicable disease surveillance and management, and the vast amount of data generated providing raw material for research and development of new therapies and diagnostics. While the advantages of pathogen genomics in public health and biomedical research are clear, pertinent challenges exist in the technological and ELSI landscape, including data governance, data archival, data sharing, informed consent and privacy, and are further complicated with biobanking and/or public health emergency situations.

In pathogen genomics, the sequences of the microbes are the target data to be investigated, however, the methodology used to obtain these sequences invariably result in ‘contamination’ with host genomic data. Where samples are obtained from a human participant, clinical data will also be captured and it is the use of this metadata along with pathogen genomic data, which is used to strengthen epidemiological insights for risk assessment, disease management and ultimately public health decision making.

Several question which are frequently raised by non-domain experts relates to guidance and clear policy for the ethical and legal use of human derived samples and clinical data in pathogen genomics as it relates to the public health sector. Furthermore, to which frameworks would complex samples and their data need to be compliant with, particularly from an ethical (such as benefit sharing) and legal prospective. Under emergency situations, such as recently experienced in the COVID-19 pandemic, should exceptions to rigid policy be permitted, and if so, should emergency response circumvent the need for some processes, and, how will this impact the use of the data for future research? What measures need to be in place to prevent exploitation and inequitable data use?

Challenge

We are asking participants to propose guidelines for data processing and sharing of pathogen data in public health under routine and emergency situations. Participants’ solutions should enable data generators to navigate ELSI requirements related to data governance in public health focused pathogen genomics. Challenge partner is specifically interested in:

- Technical and policy guidelines for use, storage and sharing of pathogen genomes and clinical metadata for surveillance and epidemiology in both routine and emergency response situations.

- Tools for non-domain experts to enhance compliance measures (e.g. checklists or ‘ask an expert’ portals).

Resources:

- Armstrong GL, MacCannell DR, Taylor J, et al. Pathogen genomics in public health. *N Engl J Med.* 2019;381(26):2569–80. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmsr1813907>.
- Geller, G., Dvoskin, R., Thio, C.L. et al. Genomics and infectious disease: a call to identify the ethical, legal and social implications for public health and clinical practice. *Genome Med* 6, 106 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-014-0106-2>
- Black, A., MacCannell, D.R., Sibley, T.R. et al. Ten recommendations for supporting open pathogen genomic analysis in public health. *Nat Med* 26, 832–841 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0935-z>
- Bedeker A, Nichols M, Allie T for the PHA4GE Ethics and Data-Sharing Working Group, et al A framework for the promotion of ethical benefit sharing in health research *BMJ Global Health* 2022;7:e008096.

Students' Solutions

Data privacy in public health context

iMPILO

QUANTUM
RESISTANT
LEDGER

A technologically-empowered
implementation of the Nagoya Protocol

iMPILO QRLEDGER

Impilo Quantum Resistant Ledger

uncompromising on benefit-sharing from medical specimen

Definitions

In this document, we use the term “**substance**” to refer to any and all biological extracts wither from a human or any other living organism. These could include blood, tissue, stem cells, mucous, tears, and the list goes. The use of the term “**genetic resources**” is in line with the legal terminologies and may be used interchangeably with the term “**substance**”.

Blockchain technology is like a digital ledger or record book that is shared across many computers. Each time a transaction is made, it gets recorded in this ledger. What makes it special is that once a transaction is recorded, it can't be changed or deleted, making it very secure and trustworthy.

Smart contracts are like digital agreements written in code. They automatically execute and enforce themselves when certain conditions are met. Think of them as "if-then" rules: if something specific happens, then the contract performs a particular action.

Medical Subject refers to the person from which a specimen was extracted from.

Service Provider refers to companies that collect substances and the health institutions like clinics and hospitals.

Solution Name/Team Name: iMPILO QRLEDGER (Impilo Quantum Resistant Ledger)

List of team members and academic advisor (if applicable):

1. Mr Bonza Majozi (Quantic Business School of Technology – Executive MBA & University of Pretoria – Honours in Engineering Technology Management)
2. Mr Vukani Majozi (University of the Witwatersrand – Master of Management in Finance and Investment)
3. Dr Hossein Masoumi Karakani (Advisor, University of Pretoria, Department of Institutional Planning – Institutional Research and Analytics)

Contact information (email and phone number) for team's point of contact

1. Bonza Majozi: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]
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[REDACTED]

Abstract/ Solution Overview (200 words, does not count toward page limit)

What is your solution? (e.g. A new law, regulation, policy, partnership or operational/ business process? A physical product, digital tool, API, etc?) What does it do? What are the key features?

Our solution, iMPILO QRLedger, is a blockchain-powered platform designed to manage medical records, genetic resources, and benefit-sharing. It facilitates the collection, storage, and sharing of medical records while ensuring compliance with national legal frameworks. Moreover, it supports the implementation of the Nagoya Protocol, ensuring fair and equitable benefit-sharing from transactions involving genetic resources and traditional knowledge.

The nature of the distributed ledger like technologies like blockchain inherently addresses some ELSI concerns which are anonymity, security, ownership and trust or credibility of the data. Blockchain also handles financial transactions gracefully which is fundamental to the Nagoya Protocol where benefit-sharing is monetary.

The nature of distributed ledger technologies like blockchain inherently addresses key ELSI concerns such as anonymity, security, ownership, and data credibility. Blockchain also efficiently handles financial transactions, which is fundamental to the Nagoya protocol's monetary benefit-sharing. Decentralization ensures transparency and trust in high-stakes transactions, transforming the way sensitive data is handled.

Smart contracts will enforce legal frameworks and procedures across various tasks and processes involved in managing medical records and genetic material sharing. This ensures consistency, reduces human error, and accelerates the entire process, providing a seamless experience for all stakeholders involved.

Value Proposition (1 page)

iMPILO QRLedger is a cutting-edge blockchain-powered platform that specifically addresses the challenge of managing and sharing medical records and genetic resources while ensuring compliance with ELSI. Our solution focuses on secure data governance, transparent benefit-sharing, and real-time patient access to medical records, directly addressing the critical need for trust and accountability in public health data management.

What aspect of the challenge does your solution address?

Our solution addresses the challenge of establishing a fair and transparent benefit-sharing model. This model ensures that medical subjects, specimens collectors, researchers, and companies are all ethically treated and compensated. By leveraging blockchain technology, we provide secure, transparent, and immutable records of consent, usage, and benefit-sharing agreements, fostering trust and accountability among all parties.

iMPILO QRLedger supports the entire value chain, allowing accurate verification of specimen ownership at any stage. While existing platforms manage medical records, iMPILO QRLedger goes further to facilitate fair benefit-sharing when specimens are sold to commercial drug developers.

Moreover, our platform addresses the Nagoya Protocol’s requirements for benefit-sharing of traditional and indigenous knowledge. It tracks medical specimens and stores related traditional knowledge, ensuring these contributions are respected and fairly compensated.

What stakeholders are involved in your solution? Which specific stakeholder(s) would benefit most from your solution?

This multifaceted approach involves various stakeholders and has national implications. The table below ranks stakeholders by the hierarchy of benefits. The primary benefactor is the medical subject. Other stakeholders, including pharmaceutical companies, researchers, and the government, are also part of the benefit-sharing model, whether monetary or non-monetary.

Table 1: Stakeholders involved on the iMPILO QRLedger ecosystem and their proposed benefits.

Stakeholder	Ranking	Benefit
Medical Subject	Primary	Access to medical history
		Access to own substance tracking
		Fair compensation based on benefit-sharing agreements
Service Providers (Health institutions and companies that collect medical specimens)	Primary	Secure and transparent ledger to manage records
		Automated benefit-sharing transactions as facilitated by smart contracts.
Researchers	Secondary	Access to database of available substances that can be used for research.
		Quality metadata about the substances.
		Anonymised data in accordance to legal frameworks.
Drug Development Companies	Secondary / Tertiary	Access to database of available substances that can be used for research.
		Quality metadata about the substances.
		Anonymised data in accordance to legal frameworks.
		Automated payment for substances and compensation for medical subject
Ministerial (Department of Health)	Tertiary	Access to information on how the policies are implemented.
South African Health Products Regulatory Authority	Tertiary	Access to information on how the policies are implemented.
Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity (Nagoya Protocol)	Other	Access to information on how the policies are implemented to advise on benefit-sharing models.

What difference would your solution make for the target end user?

iMPILO QRLedger ensures that people from which medical specimens are extracted from are both informed in how they are used and are fairly compensated in the even their specimen is used for developing commercial drugs.

Secondly, collectors of medical specimens like medical labs and health institutions can benefit from an all-inclusive solutions for managing the specimens they collected. They could also create smart contracts (mutually agreed terms) to share the specimens with researchers or to sell to pharmaceuticals. Upon selling to pharmaceutical companies for instance, such smart contracts will be automatically triggered to facilitate the transactions which in the process, will also compensate the medical subject.

In terms of the legal and regulatory bodies both in South Africa and abroad, such a platform will provide reach data that can inform policy development and reviews. It can also assist with planning to advance benefit-sharing models, informing the collective work from the Ngoya Protocol. Below is the summary of the intended impact from the users.

iMPILO QRLedger ensures that individuals from whom medical specimens are extracted are both informed about how their specimens are used and fairly compensated if their specimens are used for developing commercial drugs.

For **medical subjects**, iMPILO QRLedger provides transparency and control over their specimens and ensures they are fairly compensated through automated smart contracts when their specimens are used for financial gain.

Service providers, such as medical labs, research and health institutions, benefit from an all-inclusive solution for managing collected specimens. They can create smart contracts with researchers or sell specimens to drug developers, ensuring seamless, automated transactions and compensating medical subjects appropriately.

For **legal and regulatory bodies** in South Africa and internationally, the platform offers rich data that can inform policy development and reviews. It aids in planning to advance benefit-sharing models, ensuring that all parties are treated fairly and ethically.

In summary, iMPILO QRLedger makes a significant difference by enhancing transparency, trust, and fairness across the entire value chain of medical specimen use, from collection to commercialization.

Potential Applications/ Use Case Scenarios (1-2 pages)

Who is the target end user and how is the solution to be used? What are the anticipated benefits/outcomes/incentives for the target end user?

The main target users of iMPILO QRLedger are medical subjects and institutions that collect medical specimens (medical labs, clinics, and hospitals). Medical subjects have a compelling incentive to use the platform as it provides insights into how and by whom their specimens are used. Moreover, they receive automatic compensation if their specimens are used for commercial purposes, ensuring they are treated fairly and transparently.

For institutions that collect medical specimens, iMPILO QRLedger offers significant benefits. These institutions gain verified medical subject data and accurate specimen records, which enhance the quality and reliability of their operations. When they commercialize the specimens, the platform ensures automatic compensation for the medical subjects, assisting in compliance with benefit-sharing agreements and reducing administrative efforts.

Beyond these primary users, the platform generates data that offers unintended benefits for government and other agencies, both locally and internationally. Governments can incentivize medical labs, research institutions, and hospitals to use the platform as it provides valuable data to support planning and resource allocation at a national level. This data can also aid academic research, helping to improve the platform, policies, and benefit-sharing models. By fostering a more transparent and accountable system, iMPILO QRLedger benefits a wide range of stakeholders, promoting ethical and efficient use of medical specimens and data.

What are the strengths of your solution? What differentiates it from others? How is your solution innovative and/or novel when compared to existing solutions?

The main strengths of iMPILO QRLedger are its foundation in legal obligations, ethical standards, and a social justice approach, ensuring fairness throughout the value chain. Supported by robust, future-proof technology, such as quantum-resistant ledgers, the platform is prepared for the era of quantum computing, which will render current security measures, including traditional blockchains like Bitcoin and Ethereum, obsolete.

This solution is one of the first blockchain-like platforms to support the practical implementation of the Nagoya Protocol. It uniquely integrates legal requirements, allowing organizations to automatically comply within relevant laws through its use. This is made possible through strong collaboration with legal bodies and government departments, such as the Department of Health and the Department of Environmental Affairs.

In terms of novelty, iMPILO QRLedger leverages natural language processing (NLP) techniques to integrate all relevant information from policies and guidelines, linking them with patient data on a single platform. While there are global blockchain products managing medical records, this solution stands out by addressing the entire value chain and ensuring benefit-sharing from medical specimens. Although the Access and Benefit-sharing Clearing-House (ABSCH) exists to facilitate the Nagoya Protocol's implementation, iMPILO QRLedger goes further by enforcing benefit-sharing frameworks and integrating comprehensive data management and compliance features.

What are the potential weaknesses, vulnerabilities or constraints of your solution? How will those be addressed or mitigated? Describe the feasibility of your solution (e.g. Steps and time needed to implement).

Although the benefits of iMPILO QRLedger flow from the medical subject up to the government and global agencies, its development and implementation follow a top-down approach to ensure success. Government and private sector buy-in is crucial; without it, adoption could be delayed or constrained.

Despite this challenge, several drivers support adoption. These include the need for a systematic approach to enforcing the Nagoya Protocol transparently and legally. iMPILO QRLedger can integrate with existing systems through Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), making it easier for health and research institutions to adopt without overhauling their current systems.

Government buy-in is also essential for incentivizing the platform's use and supporting export sales to generate higher revenue.

The feasibility of iMPILO QRLedger is supported by existing frameworks and legislation, including the Protection of Private Information Act (PoPIA), the National Health Act of 2003, the South African Health Products Regulatory Authority (SAHPRA), and the Nagoya Protocol.

Additionally, we have advanced blockchain technology and experts in law, technology, and health. Established national structures already support these laws, providing a solid foundation and contact points for implementation.

Blockchain technology has advanced, and quantum-resistant ledgers have been identified as the best cryptographic solution to ensure the platform's longevity, even with the advent of quantum computers.

Timelines:

- **Consultations:** 1-2 years for comprehensive consultations with government, health institutions, and private entities to map out requirements and features.
- **Development and Testing:** 7-13 months for platform development and testing.
- **Initial Production:** The first three years post-launch will focus on perfecting functionalities and preparing for global scaling.

By ensuring strong government and private sector collaboration, iMPILO QRLedger aims to establish a sustainable, transparent, and fair benefit-sharing model for medical specimens.

What is the impact of your solution? What metrics could be used to measure the impact of your solution?

Figure 1 below shows the intended impact of such a data-informed ecosystem. Each stakeholder has metrics that can be measured against. For instance, for pharmaceuticals (commercial drug developers), (1) the number of people they have paid can be measure, (2) the research projects they are conducting from the specimens, (3) the average amount of money they paid medical subjects per specimen, (4) and the total amount that they hap paid in compensating medical subjects and medical labs.

The impact of such a law-driven approach to technology development can also be mapped in terms of the sustainable development goals (SDGs). For instance, this solution contributes directly SGD 3 (**good health** and wellbeing); to SDG 10 (**reduced inequalities**), SD 9 (industry, **innovation**, and infrastructure); SDG 16 (peace, **justice**, and **strong institutions**); and SGD 17 (**partnerships** for the goals).

In countries were giving medical specimens for financial gain like mucous for TB research, blood, tissue, stem and sperm cells, embryos and foetal tissue, this platform can play a crucial role in ensuring that medical subjects are not taken for granted and such 'donations' are done ethically without causing harm for financial gain. In such instances, iMPILO QRLedger can also contribute directly to SDG 1 (**no poverty**) and SDG 2 (**zero hunger**) due to income generation.

Figure 1: Impact overview for the iMPILO QR Ledger stakeholders. Each stakeholder has associated Metrics that can be measures. The dotted lines indicate how various stakeholders and metrics influence each other

The sustainable development goals can also be mapped according to the Africa 2063 Agenda in terms of our continental priorities.

- Aspiration 1: A Prosperous Africa Based on Inclusive Growth and Sustainable Development,
- Aspiration 3: An Africa of Good Governance, Democracy, Respect for Human Rights, Justice, and the Rule of Law,
- Aspiration 6: An Africa Whose Development is People-Driven, Relying on the Potential Offered by African People, Especially Its Women and Youth.

Assumptions and Limitations (1 page)

What assumptions did you have to make in order to design your solution? What are the limitations of your solution or what did you not have time to address?

The key assumption of this solution is that the government will support and elevate it to a national project, providing substantial backing. Additionally, the government is expected to incentivize the private sector to adopt this solution, rather than relying on punitive measures or new laws for enforcement.

Another assumption is that through consultations, transaction transparency will be maintained. Stakeholders, within their rights and permissions, should be able to access relevant data. Medical subjects, for instance, should be able to track how their specimens are used and verify adherence to agreed terms, ensuring transparency for both subjects and service providers.

Describe the prototype of your solution. What assumptions were required, or limitations exist when considering your prototype?

iMPILO QRLedger allows for the collection of both medical records and records pertaining medical specimens what were extracted from the medical subjects. All medical records are made available to the medical subjects as it is a personal right according to the PoPI Act. Medical specimens can be shared with researchers to support their research or sold to pharmaceutical companies to develop commercial drugs. In such instance, smart contracts are used to facilitate such transitions and avertedly compensate the data subject.

iMPILO QRLedger enables the collection of medical records and specimen data from medical subjects. According to the PoPI Act, medical subjects have access to their medical records as a personal right. Information about their specimens alike is within their right to know how it was used. The platform then allows for this transparency. Moreover, iMPILO QRLedger allow for adhering to legal standards which include fair and equitable benefit-sharing in the event the specimen is sold for financial gain, thus implementing the Nagoya Protocol.

It is assumed that medical subjects will use the app to view transactions related to their specimens and withdraw any financial gains deposited into their digital wallet.

Operational Requirements (½ - 1 page)

What programs, APIs, data are required to run your solution?

iMPILO QRLedger will be developed on a quantum-resistant ledger, specifically through the IOTA's Tangle technology, which is tamper-proof and resilient against quantum computing threats.

The platform offers two modes for adding initial records. The first mode allows service providers to use iMPILO QRLedger for all data collection needs, storing medical subject information directly within the platform. The second mode uses API integration to pull medical subject information from the service provider's database and link it to the records created within iMPILO QRLedger. This approach ensures that most data is generated within the platform, while necessary external data is seamlessly integrated (external data is called an oracle in blockchain).

Smart contracts will facilitate all legal requirements and tasks. For example, before drawing a blood sample, a smart contract will manage the consent to draw blood, the agreement on benefit-sharing if the specimen leads to profit, and the explanation of blood test results and any future transactions. The medical subject can then confirm their understanding and agreement, ensuring transparency and compliance through smart contracts.

Each stakeholder, including medical subjects, service providers, and government agencies, will have digital wallets to store financial gains. These wallets enable seamless and secure transactions and incentivize the use of the platform. By leveraging quantum-resistant technology and smart contracts, iMPILO QRLedger ensures a secure, transparent, and efficient ecosystem for managing medical specimens and data.

Implementation Requirements (1 pages)

What policies, budgeting, resources would be needed for a potential end-user agency or company to adopt your solution?

This solution will leverage existing policies and legislation, aiming to enforce legal frameworks through technology in medical transactions. The critical aspect is converting legal requirements into smart contracts. These smart contracts will both enforce legal compliance and facilitate normal transactions.

An onboarding service provider or agency will initially have meetings with the onboarding team to understand the platform, identify alignment, and establish a use case. Following this, the onboarding process will begin, initiated by the fees outlined in Table 2.

The terms of use and a comprehensive whitepaper, including various use cases, will be available on the platform's website to provide a clear understanding of the platform.

The budget requirements are detailed in Table 2, breaking down the costs associated with onboarding and support services.

Table 2: Onboarding fee structure.

Onboarding Components	Duration	Financial Projection
Onboarding (includes training)	1 – 3 months	R35 000 flat fee for 100 000 users (5% of the onboarding fee for 50 000 additional users)
Retention fee		20% of the onboarding fee
Technical Support (development)	Hourly	R1500
Self-help site and resources	-	-

Next Steps (1/2 - 1 pages)

If you had 3 more months to work on this solution, what would you do?

To test the feasibility and propensity for adoption, we will conduct interviews with key stakeholders, including government employees involved in relevant aspects of the solution, private and public hospitals, regular blood donors, and blockchain developers. These interviews will help us assess fit-for-use and identify considerations for moving forward. We will also consult legal experts in information governance and medical information, and obtain insights from a local representative on the implementation of the Nagoya Protocol.

Moreover, we will develop a full web-based mock-up of the system, including various apps for stakeholders. This mock-up will demonstrate how smart contracts can enforce legal compliance and ensure good data governance.

We will also research the financial and environmental sustainability of the platform, covering internal research and development needs, operations, and sales and marketing strategies. This comprehensive approach will ensure a robust and practical solution.

Estimated Budget/Cost (½ - 1 page)

The scaling of iMPILO QRLedger in South Africa will involve a task team representing the entire sector to map and update legal requirements into smart contracts. This team will standardize processes and tasks, facilitating gradual adoption by health entities.

Globally, the platform will adapt to each country's nuances, influenced by and influencing local practices, to ensure continuity and strengthen international collaboration. This approach will position South Africa as a leader in the benefit-sharing model.

The initial platform will primarily be government-funded, with additional features funded by requesting service providers. The same scaling model will apply internationally, ensuring new countries undergo similar due diligence and maintain a unified approach among stakeholders. We won't necessarily restrict where their funding may come from, but the onboarding of another country needs to follow similar due diligence as we would to ensure a united approach among all their stakeholders.

In projecting the cost of bringing such platform from the ground, we projected a cost of at least R3.7 million. The assumptions are indicated below.

Consultations with the sector: R650 000 (travel, venue bookings, catering, and accessories)

Project Setup: R250 000

Legal Research: R90 000

UI/UX Design: R650 000 (4 web apps and 1 mobile app)

Backend Development and testing & User Acceptance Testing: R1.9 million

Contingency (15%): R409 500

The projections are based on an estimate from a blockchain project that both members of this team are currently working on for a FinTech product.

Experts' Discourse

Data privacy in public health context

- **Ms Dorcas Tsebee, Tech Hive Advisory, Africa**
- **Ms Florence Ogonjo, Centre for Intellectual Property and Information Technology Law, Strathmore University, Kenya**
 - **Dr Andrew Rens, ResearchICT Africa**
 - **Dr Scott Timcke, ResearchICT Africa**

Dr Andrew Rens and Dr Scott Timcke, ResearchICT Africa

Scott and Andrew presented a form of public health solution, but from a law and political economy of tech perspective. One of the problems they identified in the health sector in relation to data privacy is the nature and imperative of surveillance capitalism and the fragile systems that are created because of data collection and processing. For them, the profit imperatives for data collection and systems connectivity result in creating systems that may be otherwise fragile because more data is collected than necessary. This may contravene data minimization principles. This type of expansionist logic creates vulnerabilities for digital networks. The same imperative or the same extension logic applies to public health care systems, raising concerns about data security because there is more data exposed to weak systems. For various reasons in South Africa, we face a numerous number of cybersecurity breaches, jeopardising public healthcare systems. Perimeter defense is often inadequate, and this means that clinical national systems are significantly vulnerable to a variety of breaches and attacks.

Addressing these breaches and attacks is an operating environment that requires being sensitive to sensitive information for personal and public health matters. However, there are a few mechanisms and institutions that can be used to address this particular type of problem especially the problem of connectedness of data giving rise to inference attacks. And this is now recognized even in the United States, which has for long claimed that consent is sufficient to protect health data.

The Federal Trade Commission (FTC) recently issued a statement pointing out that, even if someone has given consent for the release of their genetic data, this is not just data about them, it's also data about their family. The FTC concluded that while some kinds of data can be de identified, some kinds cannot, and they give DNA and other genetic data as an example. In our own context in Africa, health data is often resistant to de-identification and particularly de-identification which can survive an inference attack and, which can survive the combination of different datasets. So, although we have some countries like South Africa and a few other countries with data protection laws, or which are in the process of creating data protection laws, what we is missing is that health data do not receive particular attention.

Also lacking is a kind of standard which, deals rigorously with the issues around inference attacks and around how data collection that may have been consented to by 1 person can be used to infer things around other people and in particular, health data can be used in this way.

Solutions: There should be a standard - a policy standard, which can then be technically implemented. This standard should require notice to people giving consent of the possibilities of inference attacks, of the possibilities that their consent might impact other people. It also, should require that the data expires after a period, probably 3 years.

In terms of implementing or ensuring that the standard is enforced, one way is if technical setups of databases have to comply with the standard. Another solution is to require that

the data be held by data stewards who would ensure compliance with the standard and who may upon request by health authorities, researchers, or medical practitioners, make the data accessible or available subject to stated conditions based on the standard.

Because of the nature of cross border data transfers, such a policy standard needs to be consistently enforced and can overlap with the African Continental Free Trade Agreement, the African Data Policy Framework, and other such instruments around. Standardization on a continental level is absolutely imperative to ensure that we can have continental wide markets that can deal in health and public data.

Africa, Law & Emerging Technologies Policy Hackathon

Public Health Challenge

Presented by **Dorcas Tsebee**

July 31, 2024

University of Pretoria

Public health emergencies X privacy considerations

Public health emergencies have highlighted the importance of data protection and privacy in Africa. This is because, there is always the tendency for government to restrict individual privacy rights in the face of public health crises.

However, the use of technology in large scale processing of data to control the spread of pandemics and epidemics creates the need for data protection and privacy considerations by governments.

Privacy-related concerns in public health emergencies

- Limited transparency x lawful basis for processing
- Blurred accountability and security
- Purpose limitation
- Fear of mass surveillance
- Profiling and automated processing
- Storage limitation/retention

Mass surveillance - Recent case

Cholera outbreak in Lagos, Nigeria

“As of April 28, 2024, Nigeria reported 815 suspected cholera cases and 14 deaths across 25 states”

In response, statewide surveillance was activated, including location tracking

Samples were collected for confirmation

Ongoing cholera surveillance evaluation across all the states

Collation of data for incident response and management

Proposed solution

Leveraging the mandate of data protection authorities in the protection of personal data

- Data protection authorities (DPAs) to create awareness, train and upskill health officers
- More DPAs to issue guidance notes on the processing of personal data during public health emergencies (as seen in South Africa, Nigeria, Mauritius, Burkina Faso, Mali, Morocco, Senegal)
- Ensuring effective data management by public health authorities
- Collaboration with public health authorities and emergency response teams in handling personal data
- Developing compliance checklists for the health sector
- Reinforcing regional and national collaborations to promote enforcement of data protection laws
- Considerations for necessity and proportionality in processing personal data for public health emergency and routine situations

Examples of earlier efforts from DPAs

- The African Network of Personal Data Protection Authorities (**RAPDP**) Declaration regarding the protection of personal data in the context of the covid-19 pandemic, stressing that sensitive personal data to be subject to special precautions
- Statement from the **EDPB** on privacy during health emergencies
- **South Africa** - Guidance Note on processing personal information in the management and containment of the covid-19 pandemic in terms of POPIA
- **Nigeria** - The National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) Guidance for the management of personal data by public institutions in Nigeria. In addition, stated that COVID-19 data collection should comply with the NDPR
- **Mali** - The Personal Data Protection Authority's (APDP) warnings on the collection of personal data and the protection of people's privacy
- **Senegal** - The Data Protection Commission's (CDP) statement on the protection of personal data in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic
- **Mauritius** - Guide on data protection for health data and artificial intelligence solutions in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic
- **Tunisia** - Recommendations of the National Personal Data Protection Office relating to the protection of personal data in the COVID-19 period
- **Burkina Faso** - Message from the Information Technology and Civil Liberties Commission (CIL) on the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19)

Implementation strategies

To implement the proposed solution, the following strategies must be implemented:

1. **Research:** Publication of comprehensive research on the role of DPAs in promoting effective data protection practices during public health emergencies.
2. **Stakeholder engagements:** Engaging relevant stakeholders to discuss DPA responsibilities during health emergencies.
3. **Reinforcement:** Reinforcing DPA roles and encouraging more guidance on data processing for public health practitioners.
4. **Collaboration:** Regional and national collaboration to drive uniform enforcement of laws.

QUESTIONS

ANSWERS

Strathmore University
*Centre for Intellectual Property and
Information Technology Law*

Public Health and Governance

Data Protection in Health Data Governance.

Presented by Florence A. Ogonjo

Public Health & Data Governance

There is no question about the importance of health data, as it is categorized as sensitive personal data. In contextualizing data governance and public health, there are still struggles in understanding,

- Who “owns” the data, and who can make decisions about data;
- Where is data stored, and who can access it;
- How to ensure data quality and interoperability;
- How to protect data from threats such as inappropriate access and use, and;
- What tools, resources, and skillsets are needed to manage and use data effectively?

Health Data Governance Principles

Kenyan Context in Relation to EMR Systems

- Safeguards: While technical safeguards are included, there is a lack of comprehensive organizational measures for confidentiality, privacy, and security.
- Consent and Transparency: The Standards only reference consent in relation to electronic signatures, lacking detailed guidance on obtaining consent as specified by the DPA. I
- Lack of Guidelines: There are no specific protocols for essential areas such as data breach reporting, data retention, or the appointment of Data Protection Officers.

Regulatory Measures to Address the gaps

Digital Health Act :

- Establishes integrated health management system,
- provides for health data governance
- Establishment of health data framework
- Health data use,
- Security, privacy and disclosure of data in the system
- Retention and disposal of data in the system
- Use of sensitive personal data
- consent, in case of minors
- Right to rectification and erasure

Guidance note for the health sector

Conclusion

Although data protection is a subset of data governance, it plays a significant role in advancing and informing data governance frameworks. Additionally, it provides mechanisms through which breaches can be adequately addressed systematically, with health data being considered sensitive personal data, thus falling under data protection laws.

Excerpts from judges' feedback and audience questions/comments

Public Health

- When we speak of building capacity of data protection authorities across the continent, we need to be clear about the purpose of building capacity (i.e., capacity to do what?).
- The legal basis for data processing is not just consent. It could be public interest or vital interest or legitimate interest. In the case of a public health emergency, rarely would consent be the legal basis.
- Explaining the purpose of health data processing is not enough. It is important that to be detailed especially in explaining that in the case of genetic data, disclosure or use of data affects not just the person giving consent it affects their family members as well. However, beyond explanation, it is important to empower the data subject to use the information provided. Whether in-depth explanations of implications prior to data collection and processing address concerns around the potential [inference attacks](#) may be debatable.

Child privacy on digital platforms

- When we speak of parents, the nuclear family scenario in Africa is different from the Western scenario of parents and children. The reality is that uncles, aunts and other relatives exercise some of parental control and guidance over children in the family. Such nuance needs to be built into regulation and also expectations around implementing those regulations.
- There is a lot of debate about amending the definition of a child to lower the age of minority. The African children's charter clearly defines a child as any person below the age of 18, and that is without any exception. It is possible that altering this age in the digital sphere could actually create inconsistencies and weaken the protection mechanisms that are crucial for safeguarding the rights and safety of children.
- It could expose younger individuals to risks that they are not equipped to handle, thereby undermining their safety and well-being. An alternative to amending the age definition would be to focus efforts on enhancing digital literacy and safety measures that align with the existing legal protections for all children.
- One of the biggest challenges is how to harmonize regulation on privacy issues in Africa to have a common regulatory framework or a regulatory regime that looks similar. The current situation where every country has their own approach is very disruptive, especially for data handlers, platforms, and people seeking to make complaints or make decisions across borders.

- In South Africa, feedback from many children is that they were not happy with section 34 and 35 of the Protection of Personal Information Act especially because every level of consent needs a parent, and children want to have a say on the issue of consent. It is important that in thinking of child privacy online, children need to be consulted.

General comments

The safety of AI, the context and how it views what people input, what outputs it generates is an area for policy makers and those who work in policy must work on and continue to work on to make sure that that AI remains safe.

In the design of platforms and AI system, thought must be given to the legal implications before launching the platform or system.